

Why decode the DNA of all British and Irish species?

The Darwin Tree of Life Project sequences reference genomes for all non-bacterial species in Britain and Ireland and is projected to generate **£2.3 - 2.9 billion** for the UK economy over 30 years

AGRICULTURE

£804 million - £1.4 billion

- tackling invasive pests
- improving crop resilience
- fighting livestock parasites
- preserving fish stocks

CONSERVATION

£1.3 billion

- efficiently restoring endangered species
- developing resilience to invasive disease
- preserving pollinator populations

RESEARCH & INNOVATION

Over £170 million

through science funding reinvestment in valuable research

Technology innovations:

- Datasets for improved eDNA
- Engineering ecosystems
- Medicine and biotechnology

Analysis by Frontier Economics with a 30-year horizon: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19472560